

XSTool: an Interpolation Tool for Parametric Self-Shielded Microscopic cross-sections

M. Riva¹, E. Masiello^{1,*}, F. Filiciotto¹, G. Torlai¹, B. Vezzoni¹, R. Lenain¹

¹Université Paris Saclay, CEA, Services d'Études des Réacteurs et de Mathématiques Appliquées, 91191 Gif-sur-Yvette, France

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ABSTRACT

This work lays the foundations for an advanced two-step scheme for fission reactors calculation, based on infinite-dilution and self-shielded microscopic cross sections interpolation, without spatial homogenization. The parametric self-shielded cross-sections are generated via standard 2-D assembly simulations using APOLLO3[®], with the resonant-isotope cross-sections being stored in HDF file format, using a SHEM (281 groups) energy mesh, at each state-point. This preliminary study aims at investigating the variability of the self-shielded cross-sections within a defined multi-parameter space, as well as the possibility to factorize the dependence on burn-up. The approach is verified on a UO_x - Gd fuel-assembly case.

Keywords: Self-shielded cross-sections, multi-linear interpolation, factorization

1. INTRODUCTION

Reactor cores are generally simulated using a two-step approach. This procedure carries out detailed neutron transport calculations of 2-D fuel-assemblies types composing the reactor core before performing 3D core simulations with homogenized data. Although widely used in industrial calculation schemes, this methodology is affected by several approximations related to the first-step, such as the calculations conducted on 2-D geometries through reflective boundary conditions and the adoption of a critical leakage model to correct the spectrum necessary to homogenize in space and in energy the isotope-wise cross-sections. The paper proposes an alternative to the standard two-step approach, consisting in interpolating the infinite-dilution as well as the self-shielded microscopic cross-sections, without resorting to spatial homogenization beforehand. This article is part of the research work around the neutronics / thermal-hydraulic (TH) coupling (N-TH), presented in this conference [1]. In this context, the TH feedback is taken into account by updating the cross sections through multivariate interpolation over the parameter space. Thereby, the effective cross sections are available to feed the macroscopic cross-section library of the Integro-Differential Transport (IDT) solver of APOLLO3[®] [2]. In this study, IDT, which is a discrete-ordinate transport solver relying on short-characteristics for spatial discretization, has been recently updated with new geometrical capabilities allowing for an exact modelling of 3-D core configurations with cusping-free control-rod models [3]. In this work, the solver is used to ultimately verify cross-sections by using its stand-alone development version.

2. CROSS-SECTION GENERATION

In the present work, the interpolation of the microscopic cross-sections and the generation of the (energy-collapsed) macroscopic cross-section library are carried out using XSTool (*Cross-Section Tool*). This resorts to a capability of APOLLO3[®] [2], to generate a snapshot of the self-shielded cross-sections, material

*emiliano.masiello@cea.fr

flux distributions and isotopic concentrations, for all resonant isotopes at each burn-up step of a lattice calculation. These data are written and stored in a compressed form on a HDF (*Hierarchical Data Format*) file [4], hereafter referred as the External Parametric Library of Self-Shielding Factors (EPL-SSF), at the reference energy mesh, composed by 281, 363 or 1968 energy groups. The energy refinements are due to the reference multigroup structures available in the GALILEE software [5] that processes continuous-energy evaluation data files, in this case JEFF-3.2, to produce multigroup cross-sections libraries [5] for APOLLO3[®]. The calculation is repeated for a variety of state-points, \mathbf{p}_n , $n = 1, \dots, N_{states}$, each corresponding to a set of physical parameters, namely

$$\mathbf{p} = \{T_f, T_w, \rho_w, F/A_{conf}, C_B, BU, t, Xe\}, \quad (1)$$

where the parameters in (1) are the fuel temperature, the moderator temperature, the moderator mass density, the fuel assembly configuration (e.g., rodged / unrodged), the boron concentration, the burn-up, the time and the xenon concentration, respectively.

For each state-point, the EPL-SSF libraries store: 1) the self-shielding factors of the resonant isotopes, for five reaction types (**absorption**, **capture**, P_0 **diffusion**, **fission** and **fission production**), for all self-shielded groups; 2) the isotopic concentrations of the depleted media and the integrated multigroup 2-D lattice scalar flux of each medium. The foreseen applications of the EPL-SSF file are twofold: 1) **multi-physics simulations** with the neutron/photon transport solver receiving the thermal-hydraulic feedback on cross-sections, for critical-boron or time-dependent calculations; 2) **importance map generation** via the Integro-Differential Transport solver (IDT), in which XSTool is used as built-in neutron/photon multigroup cross-section library in the framework of TRIPOLI-4[®] CADIS/FW-CADIS variance-reduction technique [6].

In XSTool, the infinite-dilution microscopic cross-section of a non-resonant isotope ν , namely $\sigma_\nu^\infty(T)$, and the effective microscopic cross-section of a resonant isotope ι , namely $\sigma_\iota^e(T, \mathbf{p})$, are reconstructed by interpolation, as follows

$$\sigma_\nu^\infty(T) = \sum_k b_k(T) \sigma_\nu^\infty(T_k), \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_\iota^e(T, \mathbf{p}) = \sum_{l,n} g_{l,n}(T, \mathbf{p}) \sigma_\iota^e(T_l, \mathbf{p}_n), \quad (3)$$

where, to lighten the notation, the group index has been suppressed. Equation (2) interpolates the infinite-dilution cross-section, σ_ν^∞ , along the temperature points T_k of the external reference cross-section library. Therefore, the points T_k correspond to the temperatures at which the Doppler broadening was performed in GALILEE for the library. In Eq. (3), the effective microscopic cross-section

$$\sigma_\iota^e(T_l, \mathbf{p}_n) = \mu_\iota^e(T_l, \mathbf{p}_n) \sigma_\iota^\infty(T_l) \quad (4)$$

is reconstructed as the product of the infinite-dilution cross-section, $\sigma_\iota^\infty(T_l)$ which is interpolated as in Eq. (2) for each temperature point T_l required in (3), times the self-shielding factor, $\mu_\iota^e(T_l, \mathbf{p}_n)$, defined as

$$\mu_\iota^e(T_l, \mathbf{p}_n) = \frac{\sigma_\iota^e(T_l, \mathbf{p}_n)}{\sigma_\iota^\infty(T_l)}. \quad (5)$$

In Eq. (3), the values of the ratio $\frac{\sigma_\iota^e(T_l, \mathbf{p}_n)}{\sigma_\iota^\infty(T_l)}$ is computed during 2-D lattice calculation over the parameter space and stored in the EPL-SSF library for each state-point (T_l, \mathbf{p}_n) . The temperature points of the EPL-SSF file, i.e. the points T_l which are defined by the user to describe the state of the lattice in the parameter space, generally differs from the temperature points T_k characterizing the Doppler broadening of the infinite-dilution cross-section reference library.

The interpolating functions $b_k(T)_k$ in Eq. (2) are linear-tent functions, each associated to a point T_k , defined as

$$b_k(T) = \begin{cases} \frac{T-T_{k-1}}{T_k-T_{k-1}}, & T \in [T_{k-1}, T_k], \quad \frac{T_{k+1}-T}{T_{k+1}-T_k}, & T \in [T_k, T_{k+1}], \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

while, the base functions $g_{l,n}(T, \mathbf{p})_{l,n}$ are the interpolating functions associated to state-point T_l and \mathbf{p}_n of the EPL-SSF library. These functions satisfy the property $g_{l,n}(T_{l'}, \mathbf{p}_{n'}) = \delta_{ll'}\delta_{nn'}$, where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta. XSTool can handle Cartesian and sparse grids of state-points. In case of Cartesian grids, the interpolating functions, $g(T, \mathbf{p}; T_l, \mathbf{p}_n)$ of Eq. (3), are multi-linear functions obtained by the product of linear-tent functions as in (6). Otherwise, in case of unstructured grids, $g(T, \mathbf{p}; T_l, \mathbf{p}_n)$ are radial basis kernels, namely

$$g(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{x}_k) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_k\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad (7)$$

with $\mathbf{x} = (T, \mathbf{p})$ and $\mathbf{x}_k = (T_l, \mathbf{p}_n)$, while σ is defined as the standard deviation of the dataset. Alternatively, for sparse grids, the user can set a quadratic-polynomial kernel of the kind

$$g(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{x}_k) = \lambda_k(\mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{x}_k + d)^2, \quad (8)$$

with d as a regularization parameter, set as the average cosine across all points of the dataset, and λ_k as the normalization factor, i.e., $\lambda_k = \frac{1}{(\mathbf{x}_k \cdot \mathbf{x}_k + d)^2}$.

The effective macroscopic cross-section for medium m is therefore reconstructed as the sum of contributions from non-resonant isotopes, here indicated as $v \in m$, and resonant isotopes, $i \in m$,

$$\Sigma_m(T, \mathbf{p}) = \Sigma_m^\infty(T) + \Sigma_m(T, \mathbf{p}) = \sum_{v \in m} c_v \sigma_v^\infty(T) + \sum_{i \in m} c_i \sigma_i^e(T, \mathbf{p}). \quad (9)$$

with medium m characterized by the union of the sets of resonant and non-resonant isotopes.

3. BURN-UP AND FUEL TEMPERATURE FACTORIZATION

In order to test the approach, the following configuration has been considered: a 17×17 PWR un-rodged assembly characterized by 3.2%-enriched UO_X fuel and 32 gadolinium rods. The assembly is depleted up to 72 GWd/ton , by 95 burn-up steps, under nominal conditions. The remaining parameter space is explored by 64 state-points, consisting of 4 fuel temperatures, 4 moderator temperatures and 4 boron concentrations, at beginning of cycle (i.e., $BU = 0$). The state-parameters grid used in the analysis is set as follows: $T_f = \{474.4, 554, 754, 1074\}$ K, $T_w = \{424, 524, 574, 614\}$ K, $\rho_w = \{0.994, 0.804305, 0.734244, 0.68641\}$ g/cm^3 , at 155 MPa, $C_B = \{0, 600, 1000, 1600\}$ ppm. The state-points considered for the current application have been set to be around the nominal conditions. The extension to conditions representatives of accidental states will be considered for the future. The state-points have been calculated using the procedure based on *archiving* condition) and *branch* calculations. This consists in a first burn-up calculation, namely the *archive*-step, that generates the data-base containing depleted-fuel isotopic concentration at nominal conditions (here $T_f = 754$ K, $T_w = 574$ K, $\rho_m = 0.734244$ g/cm^3 , $C_B = 0$ ppm), and a second set of parallel *branch* calculations that reads the isotopic concentrations of each burn-up point from the *archive* data-base while modifies the rest of the state-parameters accordingly to user's grid. In the present study, a set of $95(\text{archive}) \times 64(\text{branch})$ state-points were generated to cover the Cartesian grid of parameters. Figure 1a-Figure 1b show the average value of the absorption cross-sections and the RMS (%) for ^{238}U and ^{239}Pu , respectively, in the outermost

ring of the UOX pin¹, for all self-shielded energy groups and for the whole set of state-points calculated using SIGAR [7], an analyst-oriented interface based on APOLLO3[®] for reactor core simulations.

Figure 1. Average microscopic absorption cross-section vs RMS (%) for two fissionable isotopes.

As observed, the ratio $RMS/\sigma \ll 5\%, \forall g \in [57, 92]$ for isotope ^{239}Pu , (Figure 1b), hence the effective cross-section shows little variability with respect to its mean value. This observation applies to ^{238}U as well, for all self-shielded energy groups, including group $g = 89$, where $\bar{\sigma}_j^g \sim 20 \cdot RMS$ exhibits its maximum variation.

Figure 2 displays the effective microscopic absorption cross-section of ^{238}U , in the innermost ring of UO_X (Figure 2a) and outermost ring UO_X/Gd (Figure 2b), as a function of BU , for 4 values of T_f , for group $g = 84$, showing the largest cross-section value.

(a) ^{238}U absorption XS in the fuel inner ring for $g = 89$.

(b) Absorption XS of ^{238}U in the fuel outer ring for $g = 84$.

Figure 2. Dependence on burn-up and fuel temperature: $\sigma_{U-238,abs}^{89/84,in/out}$ vs BU and T_f .

The maximum variation of $\sigma_{U-238,abs}^{84}$ with respect to the fuel temperature amounts to $\sim 30 \text{ pcm} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$.

As observed from the data-set, because of the bounded variation of cross-sections, we propose here a factorization of the interpolation accruing in the computation of the self-shielding factor. Let us recall the definition of the self-shielding factor for one energy group, $\mu_j^e(BU, T) = \sigma_j^e(BU, T) / \sigma_j^\infty(T)$, where all parameters are fixed, except for the burn-up and the local fuel temperature. One may observe that most of the dependence on T is contained in $\sigma_j^\infty(T)$, due to Doppler effect. Hence, we propose the following approximation:

$$\mu_j^e(BU, T) \approx \lambda_j^e(BU) \cdot \eta_j^e(T). \quad (10)$$

Given $T = T^*$, where T^* is taken as the nominal temperature, one has

$$\frac{\sigma_j^e(BU, T^*)}{\sigma_j^e(BU = 0, T^*)} \approx \frac{\lambda_j^e(BU) \cdot \eta_j^e(T^*) \cdot \sigma_j^\infty(T^*)}{\lambda_j^e(BU = 0) \cdot \eta_j^e(T^*) \cdot \sigma_j^\infty(T^*)} = \frac{\lambda_j^e(BU)}{\lambda_j^e(BU = 0)}. \quad (11)$$

By setting $\lambda_j^e(BU = 0) = 1$, Eq. (11) becomes

$$\frac{\sigma_j^e(BU, T^*)}{\sigma_j^e(BU = 0, T^*)} \approx \lambda_j^e(BU). \quad (12)$$

This approximation, henceforth referred as $BU - T$ factorization, is supported by Figure 3, displaying the relative error, defined as

$$\epsilon_{\%}(BU, T) = \left(1 - \frac{\lambda_j^e(BU) \cdot \eta_j^e(T)}{\mu_j^e(BU, T)} \right) \times 100\%, \quad (13)$$

for the ^{238}U microscopic absorption cross-section within the outer ring of the UO_x/Gd rod, for two energy groups of interest, ($g = 83, 84$), within the resonant interval. As depicted in Figure 3, the relative error does not exceed a few pcm .

Figure 3. $BU - T$ factorization. Relative difference, i.e., $\epsilon_{\%}$ (Eq. (13)), observed for $\sigma_{U-238,abs}^g$ ($g = 83$ on the left-hand side, $g = 84$ on the right-hand side), as a function of BU , for four different values of fuel temperature.

3.1. Extension to multivariate cross-section interpolation

Let us simplify the notation by setting the vector $\Theta = (T_f, T_w, \rho_m, C_B)$. In this context, the effective self-shielded cross-section of isotope i at a point (BU, Θ) is reconstructed as

$$\sigma_i^e(BU, \Theta) = \lambda_i^e(BU) \left\{ \sigma_i^e(BU_I, \Theta) \frac{BU_{I+1} - BU}{BU_{I+1} - BU_I} + \sigma_i^e(BU_{I+1}, \Theta) \frac{BU - BU_I}{BU_{I+1} - BU_I} \right\}, \text{ for } BU \in [BU_I, BU_{I+1}], \quad (14)$$

where $\lambda_i^e(BU)$ is the burn-up shape function computed under nominal conditions, namely

$$\Theta^* = (T_f = 754K, T_w = 574K, \rho_m = 0.734244 \text{ g/cm}^3, C_B = 0 \text{ ppm}), \quad (15)$$

as

$$\lambda_i^e(BU) = \frac{\sigma_i^e(BU, \Theta^*)}{\sigma_i^e(0, \Theta^*)}. \quad (16)$$

In Eq. (16), the effective microscopic cross-section $\sigma_i^e(BU, \Theta^*)$ is reconstructed at point BU , by linear interpolation, over the fine burn-up steps (here 95 points) stored in the library. The second term (in braces) of the RHS of Equation (14) is the cross section obtained by applying the interpolation on the coarse burn-up grid. In Equation (14), cross-sections $\sigma_i^e(BU_I, \Theta)$ and $\sigma_i^e(BU_{I+1}, \Theta)$ are evaluated by multivariate interpolation along the Θ -hyperplane (perpendicular to the BU axis). Thereby, these values are available for linear burn-up interpolation at current BU point. In this context, $\lambda_i^e(BU)$ performs as a correction factor for the multivariate interpolated cross-section on the coarse-BU parameter grid.

3.2. Preliminary results obtained using the parametric library of self-shielding factors (EPL-SSF)

Table I reports the comparison between a set of 2-D lattice simulations by APOLLO3[®] with “exact” (not-interpolated) cross-sections obtained by fine depletion simulation of the assembly at the check point

$$\Theta = (T_f = 820 \text{ K}, T_w = 614 \text{ K}, \rho_w = 0.68641 \text{ g/cm}^3, C_B = 0 \text{ ppm})$$

and a set of XSTool + IDT calculations with interpolated cross sections using $BU - T$ factorization on a EPL-SS data-set. The reference cross sections used in APOLLO3[®] simulations were generated by performing the *archive* step at check-point Θ . At this stage, APOLLO3[®] performs at each burn-up point: 1) the state-parameter setting at check point Θ ; 2) the self-shielding calculation of the lattice by Multi-Cell current-coupled collision probabilities, with Fine Structure model, using 281-group P_0 transport-corrected cross-sections; 3) a TDT-MOC lattice calculation, with 281-group P_1 cross; 4) fuel depletion and update of isotopic concentrations. As shown in the first column of Tab. I, 9 burn-up check points were selected as *branch* points. On the other side, the data-set contained in the EPL-SSF file were constructed by taking advantage of the $BU - T$ factorization. More precisely, the file contains 95 state-points, under nominal condition Θ^* given in 15, plus 6×64 points for the parameters T_f , T_m , ρ_m , and C_B , at 6 selected burn-up points, namely $BU_I \in \{0, 75, 1750, 10000, 20000, 40000\}$ MWd/ton, subsequently denoted by a subscript I , assuming values from 0 to 5. The correction factor $\lambda_i^e(BU)$ of Equation (14) were obtained using 95 burn-up points depleting at Θ^* and repeating at each time step APOLLO3[®] items 1)-3) while appending the necessary data to the EPL-SSF output file. Then, a second set of 6×64 *branch* calculations (in *reprise*-step) were performed to obtain data for the remaining state points.

The interpolation by XSTool has been verified by performing SN transport simulations using IDT linear-short characteristics with 12×6 Chebyshev-Legendre angular quadrature [8] for the 9 burn-up check points shown in Tab. I, with cross-sections interpolated at Θ . As shown in Table I, the reactivity difference between APOLLO3[®] and XSTool + IDT does not generally exceed ± 100 pcm. The pin-power

Table I. APOLLO3® vs XSTool+IDT, for a 2D 3.2% UO_x-Gd32

BU [$\frac{MWd}{ton}$]	A3®	XSTool+IDT	δk_{inf} (pcm)	max pin-power diff. (%)
100	0.85430	0.85365	76	0.9
500	0.83595	0.83529	78	1.2
3500	0.86070	0.86127	-66	0.6
8500	0.88948	0.89021	-82	0.5
13500	0.91918	0.91980	-67	0.3
18500	0.95639	0.95750	-116	0.8
47000	0.98895	0.98830	65	0.4
57000	0.85999	0.86015	-18	0.8
72000	0.75946	0.76018	-94	0.7

Table II. Memory occupation of the parametric HDF file (EPL-SSF) for several lattice types.

3.2%-enriched UO _x assembly	Memory (MB)	Memory/state-point (MB)
rod-out	19	0.47
AIC	30	0.33
B4C	22	0.29
Gd32-rod-out	56	0.85
Gd32-AIC	68	1.06
Gd32-B4C	60	0.93

error is at most 1.2%. Table II reports the memory occupation of the EPL-SSF file, for several PWR fuel assembly types. Each dataset contains the results of the lattice calculations performed by APOLLO3®, corresponding to a series of 3.2%-enriched UO_x assemblies. The parameter space is explored by the 64 state-points sketched previously.

Table III contains the memory occupation for a depleted UO_x-Gd32 assembly, with burn-up reaching 72 GWd/ton, discretized by 95 points. The table also shows the total amount of memory of the library used to perform the calculations using XSTool + IDT in Tab. I.

Considering 3 control-rod configurations per assembly, i.e., rod-out, B₄C and AIC, we can estimate to need approximately 300 to 500 MB to cover the parameter space of each assembly and a few GB of data for a full core simulation. It should be noted that one state-point for pin-by-pin homogenized cross-sections with 4 energy groups occupies almost the same amount of memory as one point of the EPL-SSF library, while almost 9 times as much are required for pin-by-pin homogenized cross-sections with 26-group energy mesh, [9].

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we present preliminary results obtained by interpolating the self-shielded cross-sections over the state parameter space. This offers a number of advantages: first, homogenization is avoided; second, given the small number of resonant isotopes and the limited number of self-shielded groups (typically less than 100, over 281 energy meshes), and considered the small number of reactions (5

Table III. Memory occupation of the EPL-SSF file for a depleted UO_x-Gd32 assembly.

N. of points	Memory (MB)
95	41
95 + 6 × 64 = 479	377

in our case, avoiding the storage of transfer matrices), the memory footprint of the libraries may be reduced (does not exceed 60 MB per assembly type) and becomes competitive with pin-by-pin homogenized libraries involving 26 energy groups; third, the EPL-SSF files together with the infinite-dilution isotope reference library produced by GALILEE allows for the reconstruction of microscopic reference reaction rates that can be used for equivalence-based energy-collapsing techniques. Furthermore, the energy condensation functionality of XSTool allows the production of effective macroscopic cross-sections with a reduced number of groups by neutron flux weighting. We have shown a first verification test using BU-T factorization which further reduces the memory footprint of the EPL-SSF files without degrading the accuracy of the calculation, with the reactivity relative difference being less than 100 pcm and the power-distributions relative difference not exceeding 1%. The use of XSTool in a multiphysics framework is under investigation. A first example is proposed in [1] showing first results for neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupling for a 3-D assembly case.

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REFERENCES

- [1] E. Masiello, F. Filiciotto, B. Vezzoni, R. Lenain, M. Riva, and G. Torlai. "Thermal-Hydraulics and Critical Boron Search Embedded in NeutronicsPower Iterations." In *PHYSOR 2026 - The International Conference on Physics of Reactors · Torino, Italy · April 19 – 23, 2026*. Torino, Italy (2026).
- [2] P. Mosca et al. "APOLLO3[®]: Overview of the New Code Capabilities for Reactor Physics Analysis." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, volume 199(sup1), pp. S17–S30 (2025).
- [3] F. Filiciotto, E. Masiello, S. Cochet-Lapuerta, and R. Lenain. "Nonconforming Three-Dimensional Model for PWR Control Rod Movements Without Homogenization and Cusping Effect." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, volume 197(9), pp. 2425–2445 (2023). URL <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00295639.2022.2151783>.
- [4] M. Poinot. "Five Good Reasons to Use the Hierarchical Data Format." *Computing in Science and Engineering*, volume 12(5), pp. 84–90 (2010).
- [5] M. Coste-Delclaux, C. Jouanne, F. Moreau, and C. Mounier. "GALILÉE-1: a validation and processing system for ENDF-6 and GND evaluations." In *EPJ Web of Conferences*, volume 111, p. 06005. EDP Sciences (2016).
- [6] M. Nowak, D. Mancusi, D. Sciannandrone, E. Masiello, H. Louvin, and E. Dumonteil. "Accelerating Monte Carlo Shielding Calculations in TRIPOLI-4 with a Deterministic Adjoint Flux." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, volume 193, pp. 1–16 (2019).
- [7] N. Gérard Castaing, E. Ménédeu, B. Mathon, A. Rouchon, and N. Zaim. "SIGAR: An APOLLO3-Based Framework for PWR Analysis." In *Proceedings International Conference on Mathematics and Computational Methods Applied to Nuclear Science and Engineering (M&C 2025)*, pp. 356–365. ANS (2025).
- [8] E. Masiello, R. Lenain, and W. Ford. "3D heterogeneous Cartesian cells for transport-based core simulations." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, volume 142, p. 107364 (2020).
- [9] S. Szames, A. Karim, D. Tomatis, and J.-M. Martinez. "FEW-GROUP CROSS SECTIONS MODELING BY ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS." *EPJ Web of Conferences*, volume 247, p. 06029 (2021).